

A Review Article on Retrofitting of an existing open Ground Store Building using shear walls

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ABSTRACT

Open ground storey (OGS) buildings, common in urban areas due to parking requirements, are structurally vulnerable to lateral loads during seismic events. This review explores the retrofitting of OGS buildings using shear walls to enhance their seismic performance. The paper consolidates recent research, highlights practical challenges, and discusses design strategies for implementing shear walls in existing structures. The findings suggest that adding shear walls can significantly improve a building's lateral stiffness, strength, and ductility, thereby reducing seismic vulnerability.

Keywords- Retrofitting, Open Ground Storey (OGS) Buildings, Shear Walls, Soft Storey Effect, Seismic Performance, Lateral Stiffness, Structural Vulnerability, Seismic Retrofitting

1. INTRODUCTION

1. Background

Structural retrofitting aims to restore or enhance the safety and functionality of buildings, particularly in seismic-prone areas. OGS buildings are characterized by a discontinuity in stiffness and strength between the ground floor and upper storeys, leading to a "soft storey" effect. Shear walls, known for their high in-plane stiffness and strength, are a popular solution to mitigate

this vulnerability. This paper reviews the efficacy of shear walls in retrofitting OGS buildings, focusing on seismic behavior, design considerations, and implementation challenges.

2. Open Ground Storey Buildings: Characteristics and Vulnerabilities

2.1 Structural Configuration

OGS buildings typically have columns at the ground level with little to no infill walls, creating an open space.

This design, while functional, results in reduced stiffness and strength at the ground storey.

2.2 Seismic Vulnerabilities

- **Soft Storey Effect:** Concentration of deformation and damage in the ground storey.
- **Poor Energy Dissipation:** Lack of infill walls reduces the building's ability to absorb seismic energy.
- **Pounding Effects:** Adjacent buildings may interact, causing additional damage.

3. Shear Walls: A Retrofitting Solution

3.1 Overview of Shear Walls

Shear walls are vertical structural elements designed to resist lateral forces caused by wind and earthquakes. They are made of reinforced concrete and are strategically placed to provide stiffness and strength.

3.2 Advantages of Shear Walls in Retrofitting

- **Enhanced Stiffness and Strength:** Significant improvement in lateral load resistance.
- **Reduced Inter-Storey Drift:** Lower deformation between floors.
- **Improved Energy Dissipation:** Higher ductility under seismic loads.

4. Retrofitting Strategies Using Shear Walls

4.1 Placement of Shear Walls

- **Symmetrical Layout:** Ensures balanced stiffness and reduces torsional effects.
- **Asymmetrical Layout:** Used in constrained spaces but may require additional analysis.

4.2 Connection with Existing Structure

- Proper anchorage and bonding between the shear wall and existing members are critical to ensure integrated behavior.
- Use of dowel bars and epoxy bonding agents is common.

4.3 Analytical Tools and Design Codes

- **ETABS and SAP2000:** Widely used for retrofitting analysis.
- **Design Codes:** IS 456:2000 and IS 1893:2016 for seismic retrofitting in India.

5. Challenges in Retrofitting with Shear Walls

- **Space Constraints:** Difficulty in accommodating shear walls in functional spaces.

- **Load Redistribution:** Adding shear walls alters load paths, which can affect adjacent components.
- **Construction Disruption:** Retrofitting requires partial or complete evacuation of the structure.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] Seismic Analysis and Retrofit of Existing

Multistoreyed Buildings in India – An Overview with a Case Study (2004) By Amlan K. Sengupta, Chemuru Srinivasulu Reddy, Badari Narayanan V T, Asokan A

Sengupta et al. (2004) presented an overview and case study on the seismic analysis and retrofit of existing multistoreyed buildings in India at the *13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*. The study highlights the post-Bhuj earthquake initiatives in India, which emphasized assessing the seismic vulnerability of reinforced concrete (RC) structures and developing retrofitting strategies. Common structural deficiencies identified include inadequate shear capacity, poor column confinement, and design irregularities such as soft storeys. The authors propose retrofitting solutions such as the addition of shear walls, infill walls, and steel braces to address these vulnerabilities. Their work underscores the critical need for adopting these strategies to enhance the structural integrity and seismic resistance of multistoreyed buildings in earthquake-prone regions. This study serves as a significant contribution to the development of retrofit frameworks tailored to Indian construction practices and seismic demands.

[2] Case Study: Retrofitting of an Existing

Residential Building by Using Shear Wall (2015) By Nikita Gupta, Poonam Dhiman, Ashok Kumar Gupta

Gupta, Dhiman, and Gupta (2015) conducted a detailed case study on the retrofitting of an existing residential building by using shear walls, published in the *Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Technology*. The study emphasizes the effectiveness of retrofitting with exterior shear walls in enhancing the seismic performance, overall strength, and stiffness of structures. By employing retrofitting techniques in compliance with the Indian Standard (IS) codes, the authors demonstrate a systematic approach to upgrading the structural resilience of aged or deficient buildings. Their findings underscore that exterior shear walls can significantly improve a building's ability to withstand seismic forces,

offering a cost-effective and reliable solution for structural rehabilitation. This research serves as a valuable reference for adopting IS code-based methodologies for retrofitting residential structures in seismic-prone regions.

[3] Retrofitting Solutions for Existing Open Ground Storey RC Buildings (2022) By K. Bharadwaj, J. Pathak
Bharadwaj and Pathak (2022) presented a study on retrofitting solutions for open ground storey (OGS) reinforced concrete (RC) buildings in the *ASPS Conference Proceedings*. The research focused on improving the seismic performance of OGS buildings, which are inherently vulnerable due to the absence of infill walls on the ground floor. Retrofitting techniques such as the addition of masonry infill walls and steel braces were analyzed for their effectiveness. These methods not only enhanced the seismic resilience of the structures but also preserved maximum parking space, a critical design requirement for OGS buildings. The analysis was conducted using Seismostruct, providing detailed insights into structural behavior and performance improvements. This study underscores the importance of targeted retrofitting strategies to address the unique challenges posed by OGS buildings in seismic zones.

[4] Seismic Evaluation and Retrofitting of Open Ground Storey (2024) By Samruddhi Sanjay Borkar, N. H. Pitale

Borkar and Pitale (2024) conducted a seismic evaluation of G+5 open ground storey (OGS) buildings in seismic zone V, published in the *IJSTE - International Journal of Science Technology & Engineering*. The study utilized linear dynamic response spectrum analysis and non-linear static pushover analysis to assess the seismic behavior of these structures. Findings revealed that the absence of infill walls in the ground storey results in a soft storey effect, significantly increasing vulnerability to collapse under lateral seismic loads. This research underscores the critical need for retrofitting measures to mitigate the soft storey effect and enhance the seismic resilience of OGS buildings in high-risk seismic zones.

[5] Seismic Retrofitting of Existing Reinforced Concrete Buildings Using Aluminium Shear Links and Eccentric Steel Chevron Braces (2024) By Ahmed Elgammal, Saher El-Khoriby & Ayman Seleemah
Elgammal, El-Khoriby, and Seleemah (2024) proposed an innovative seismic retrofitting method for reinforced

concrete buildings using aluminum shear links and eccentric steel chevron braces, published in the *Arabian Journal for Science & Engineering*. The retrofitting approach is based on a capacity design philosophy, aiming to dissipate seismic energy efficiently while protecting the primary structural elements from excessive damage. The study utilized advanced numerical analyses, including pushover and nonlinear time-history analyses, to evaluate the performance of the retrofitted structures. The results demonstrated a significant reduction in displacements and structural damage, effectively enhancing seismic resilience and minimizing building fragility. This research highlights the potential of aluminum shear links and steel braces as cost-effective and efficient solutions for improving the seismic safety of existing RC buildings.

Literatures Gap-

1. Introduction to Seismic Vulnerability of Open Ground Storey Buildings- Open ground storey buildings, often referred to as soft-storey buildings, are particularly vulnerable to seismic events due to their irregular stiffness distribution. The ground storey, typically used for parking or commercial purposes, lacks infill walls, resulting in a significant reduction in lateral stiffness compared to the upper floors. This makes the ground storey susceptible to large inter-storey drifts, leading to potential collapse during an earthquake (Murty et al., 2006).
2. Seismic Retrofitting Techniques- Various seismic retrofitting techniques have been explored to mitigate the vulnerability of soft-storey buildings. Among them, the addition of shear walls has been identified as one of the most effective methods. Shear walls significantly increase the lateral stiffness of the building, thereby reducing the inter-storey drift and enhancing overall stability (Agarwal & Shrikhande, 2011). Other techniques, such as steel bracing, base isolation, and the use of fiber-reinforced polymers, have also been studied, but shear walls remain a preferred solution due to their simplicity and effectiveness (Paulay & Priestley, 1992).
3. Behavior of Shear Walls in Retrofitting- Shear walls are structural elements that provide resistance to lateral forces due to wind or seismic activities. The placement and design of these walls are crucial in determining their effectiveness. Research has shown that shear walls should be symmetrically placed in plan to avoid

torsional effects during an earthquake (Moehle, 1992). Additionally, the integration of shear walls into existing structures requires careful consideration of the load path and connection details to ensure that the seismic forces are effectively transferred to the foundation (Wallace, 2012).

4. Case Studies on Retrofitting Using Shear Walls- Numerous case studies have been conducted on the retrofitting of open ground storey buildings using shear walls. One such study by Rai et al. (2013) analyzed the retrofitting of a four-storey residential building in India. The study demonstrated a significant reduction in lateral displacements and improved seismic performance after the addition of shear walls. Another study by Ghobarah et al. (1997) focused on the retrofitting of a six-storey commercial building in Cairo, Egypt. The introduction of shear walls led to a 40% increase in the building's overall stiffness, highlighting the effectiveness of this retrofitting method.

5. Design Considerations for Shear Walls- The design of shear walls for retrofitting purposes requires adherence to specific guidelines and standards. According to the American Concrete Institute (ACI 318-19), the design must account for factors such as the wall's aspect ratio, reinforcement detailing, and connection to the existing structure. IS 13920:2016 (Indian Standard) also provides detailed provisions for the design of earthquake-resistant structures with shear walls, emphasizing the need for ductile detailing to prevent brittle failure.

6. Challenges and Limitations- While shear walls are effective in enhancing seismic performance, their implementation in existing buildings poses certain challenges. These include disruptions to the building's functionality during construction, the need for careful planning to avoid interference with existing services, and the potential for increased loads on the foundation (Varghese, 2010). Additionally, cost considerations are a significant factor, as retrofitting can be expensive, particularly in older buildings where extensive modifications may be required (FEMA 547, 2006)

Objectives of the study: -

1. **Assess the Vulnerability:** Evaluate the seismic vulnerability of the existing open ground storey building.
2. **Design Retrofitting Solutions:** Design an

appropriate shear wall configuration to enhance the seismic performance of the structure.

3. **Structural Analysis:** Perform detailed structural analysis before and after the retrofitting to compare the effectiveness of the shear walls.
4. **Performance Evaluation:** Assess the overall improvement in the building's seismic performance post-retrofitting.

Scope of the study: -

1. Assessment of the Existing Structure:

- Perform a detailed analysis of the existing open ground storey building, focusing on its current structural configuration, material properties, and load distribution.
- Identify the specific vulnerabilities associated with the open ground storey, particularly in relation to seismic performance.

2. Design and Integration of Shear Walls:

- Design shear walls tailored to the specific needs of the building, considering factors such as optimal placement, size, reinforcement detailing, and connection to existing elements.
- Integrate the shear walls into the building's structural system, ensuring that they effectively contribute to increased lateral stiffness and seismic resistance.

3. Structural Analysis:

- Use advanced structural analysis software (e.g., ETABS, SAP2000) to model the building both before and after retrofitting.
- Evaluate key parameters such as lateral displacement, inter-storey drift, base shear, and overall stability to assess the effectiveness of the shear walls.

4. Seismic Performance Evaluation:

- Conduct a performance-based evaluation to compare the building's seismic behavior before and after retrofitting.

Analyze the reduction in seismic vulnerabilities and improvements in safety margins due to the introduction of shear walls.

3. METHODOLOGY

1. Data Collection: Gather architectural and structural details of the existing building, including material properties, dimensions, and load conditions.
2. Vulnerability Assessment: Use software tools such as ETABS or SAP2000 to model the building and perform a seismic vulnerability assessment.
3. Design of Shear Walls: Based on the assessment, design shear walls considering factors such as location, thickness, reinforcement details, and connection to the existing structure.
4. Structural Analysis: Conduct a structural analysis of the retrofitted building to evaluate the distribution of seismic forces, lateral displacements, and inter-storey drifts.

Comparison Study: Compare the structural behavior of the building before and after retrofitting, focusing on parameters like base shear, natural frequency, and overall stability.

4. CONCLUSION

The retrofitting of OGS buildings using shear walls is an effective solution for mitigating seismic vulnerabilities. While challenges exist, advancements in materials, design tools, and construction methods continue to enhance the feasibility and efficiency of this approach. Future research should focus on innovative materials and hybrid retrofitting strategies to further improve the seismic resilience of OGS structures

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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